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Impact Factor: 2.525

DOI: <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.417645>

Cite this paper as: *Kasim M, Zaidi Z.H & Shagufta B.H (2017). NON-HYDROLYTIC ROUTE TO POROUS SOL-GEL SILICA, International Journal of Education & Applied Sciences Research, Vol.4, Issue 01, Jan-2017, pp 45-51 ISSN: 2349 -2899 (Online) , ISSN: 2349 -4808 (Print), <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.417645>*

NON-HYDROLYTIC ROUTE TO POROUS SOL-GEL SILICA

Mohammad Kasim

Research Scholar,
Department Of Physics
Al-Falah School of Engg. & Tech.
Dhauj, Faridabad, Haryana, India

Prof (Dr.) Z.H. Zaidi

Ph.D Guide,
Al-Falah School of Engg. & Tech.
Dhauj, Faridabad, Haryana, India

Prof (Dr.) Shagufta B. Husain,

HoD, Department of Physics
Al-Falah School of Engg. & Tech.
Dhauj, Faridabad, Haryana, India

Abstract

A new route for the synthesis of porous sol-gel silica is proposed. Highly transparent, mechanical stable porous sol gel silica glasses were prepared using TEOS, formamide and HCl only. Our samples show the same mechanical and optical properties as reported already by others, using conventional procedure with water and alcohol.

Keywords: Aerogel, porous glass, sol gel preparation.

1. Introduction

Sol-gel technology has triggered the birth (1-2) of the new class of materials with application in two major domains: optically active materials and chemically active materials with good optical properties. Examples of the former include fillers, luminescent materials, light guides, laser components, and variety of materials for information processing and recording purpose (2). Examples of the later include a wide variety of sensors, bioactive sol-gel matrices in which enzymes are trapped, photoactive materials and catalysts. Recently, some researcher have fabricated dye doped porous sol-gel silica as a sensor for explosive detection (3-5).

The sol-gel process provide a low temperature rout for the production of high quality inorganic glasses [6-8]. The starting materials in this process is the sol: a colloid of silica alkoxide particles in alcohol solvent. If sol losses its mobility and becomes able to maintain its

shape ; this means that the sol has formed gel. Gel is a solid, usually soft and with low elastic modulus, it may not differ from the parent sol in its composition and solid to liquid ratio or it may appear to expulse part of the liquid and appear to be immersed in this liquid. The addition of a drying agent causes the colloid particles to hydrolyze and when a critical temperature is reached the particle link together in fibrillar chains [9]. The chain link to form a three dimensional network in the liquid phase and the accompanying less of freedom is defined as the onset of gelation.

Generally the sol-gel process for sol-gel derived silica is represented by .

Where A is an alkyl group. Tetramethyl orthosilicate or tetraethyl orthosilicate is commonly used alkoxides. The sol-gel process based on the hydrolysis/polycondensation is one of the commonly used method for the synthesis of porous sol-gel silica. Acid or base can be used as a catalyst.

In 1987 [10] addition of alcohol was shown as an unnecessary ingredient. It is well know that water is a necessary ingredient added for hydrolysis [11] and alcohol is used for increasing homogeneity of the solution. But in the last decade non-hydrolytic sol-gel process [12-16] has been recognized as a useful route for the synthesis of sol-gel materials. In this letter we report the synthesis of sol-gel silica without using water and alcohol, only TEOS, formamide and HCl are found sufficient to obtain transparent, homogeneous and mechanical stable, crack free porous xerogel.

2. Experimental

The following chemicals have been used in the experimental work for the preparation of sol-gel silica : Tetraetoxysilane (TEOS) (Acros Organic, USA,98% pure), Formamide (LR Grade, Central Drug House (P) Ltd. New Delhi, India, 98.5%), Hydrochloric acid(Changshu Yangyuan Chemical China). We take initial solution typically composed of 15 ml of tetraetoxysilane (TEOS), 12.5 ml of formamide and 2 ml of hydrochloric acid serving as catalyst. This solution was kept at 60⁰C in cylindrical plastic tubes. After one week, tubes were opened for the evaporation of expelled liquid and the sample were dried for another week at the same temperature.

Results and Discussion

The main aim of this letter is to simplify the synthesis procedure of sol gel silica and to draw attention of the readers towards the reaction kinetics for better understanding. In our case, how the basic reaction (hydrolysis and condensation without water) had occurred will be published elsewhere. (as pH value and the procedure have profound effects on the structure of the gel).

A perfectly transparent and crack free disc (14 mm x 10 mm) was obtained (fig.1) with an apparent density of 1.45 gm/cm³, which is similar to the density of sol-gel silica prepared with other previously reported procedures (Table-1).

Table-1.

Chemicals Used in Sol-Gel porous	Density (gm/cm ⁻¹)	UV-Cutoff (nm)	References
TEOS+Water+Alcohol+Formamide+HNO ₃	1.39	207	[8]
TEOS+Methylalcohol+Formamide+ HNO ₃	1.38	590	[17]
PMMA(MAPTMS)+TEOS+Titaniumisopropoxide	1.20	275	[18]
UV Grade Fused Silica	2.202	195	
TEOS+Formamide+HCl	1.45	210	

Fig.1 Snapshots of sol-gel silica glass sample

Fig.2. Transmittance spectrum of sol-gel silica prepared by a mixture of TEOS, formamide and HCl only

As the solvents escape from within the gel the changes occur in pore size during these process and stress is produced in the silica gel network that may cause cracking. Here, in this work we have tried to overcome this problem by the use of chemical additive to reduce the stress in gelled sample. It has been observed the formamide reduce cracking that help to convert the wet silica gel into monolithic gel within a reasonable time.

Fig.2 represents the transmission spectrum. This spectrum was measured with a Perkin Elmer UV-vis-NIR spectrometer within the range of 200-1000 nm. Our sample shows improved UV-cutoff which is most desirable property of porous sol-gel silica for doping of any optically active materials within these gels. These observation clearly indicate that pore structure of our samples is not very different from that of prepared by the process using water and alcohol.

Fig.3. DSC curves of pure silica glass.

Figure.3 represents the differential scanning calorimetry (DSC) study at heat flow rate of 10^0 C/min. It has been observed that the prepared samples show the good thermal stability from 100^0 C to 150^0 C without any significant change in the shape.

Fig.4- FTIR spectra of pure silica glass

The objective of the IR study was to observe the structural bonding formation for better mechanical and optical properties. The FTIR spectra of prepared porous sol-gel silica shows several peaks shown in Fig.4. The shoulders at 3388 cm⁻¹ and 3210 cm⁻¹ is mainly due to combination of Si-OH. A weak absorption band is seen at 1691 cm⁻¹ due to the stretching vibration of -OH. The absorption band in the region 1691 cm⁻¹ to 1348 cm⁻¹ is associated with stretching of C=O and C-H networks. The main bands in the region 1100 cm⁻¹ to 400 cm⁻¹ corresponding to stretching of Si-O-Si network. The Si-O-Si fundamental vibrations give the strong band at 1078 cm⁻¹ and 564 cm⁻¹ respectively.

Conclusion:

In conclusion, we have synthesized porous sol-gel silica using tetraethylorthosilicate (TEOS), formamide and HCl only. Alcohol and water were shown as an unnecessary components in the proposed new sol-gel process for the fabrication of porous sol-gel silica. Our samples show the comparable mechanical and optical properties with the conventional porous sol-gel silica prepared using water and alcohol. We strongly believe these kinds of results have not been previously reported elsewhere.

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